

H2020-FNR-2020-2 Project no. 101000560

Rapid discovery and development of enzymes for novel and greener consumer products

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Start date: 01-06-2021

Duration: 4 years

D6.3 – Plan for dissemination and exploitation of results (PEDR) – 2nd version.

Work Package N°:	6
Deliverable N°:	6.3
Lead Beneficiary:	SUSMOM / SCS
Other participants:	
Version:	1.0
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Dissemination level:	Public
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The Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PDER) focuses on the project objectives and impact. Besides Research, Development and Demonstration activities, Protection, Exploitation and Dissemination must also be addressed for the consortium's success. Activities are planned in compliance with the desired impact and updated during the project. D6.3 is the second version of the plan. Protection and Exploitation (WP6), and Communication and Dissemination (WP7), are interconnected. These two WPs may be considered as parts of a company. WP6 would represent the "Business Development Unit", and WP7 would perform as the "Communication and Marketing Department". The interconnections of both WPs pave the way to go from Results-to-Impact. Key-to-success is the continuous feedback between these WPs. Furthermore, in addition to exploitation and dissemination, D6.3 includes an overview of the planned communication actions within the project. Communication forms the basis for dissemination, and the tools, channels and formats envisioned in the communication plan can be used also for the dissemination. The RADICALZ's expected impact is to strengthen the competitiveness of the (European) (bio)chemical industry while at the same time making positive contributions to society, industry and the economy by:

- Generating scientific knowledge, new enzymes, and beyond state-of-the-art microfluidic techniques for the discovery and optimization of new biocatalysts.
- Introducing in markets (e.g. nutraceuticals, food industry, bulk chemicals, etc.), with novel biocatalytic concepts, and developing tailored specific enzyme panels.
- Contributing to create qualified-jobs by training new generations of scientists.
- Developing more environment-friendly processes, with considerations related to Green Chemistry metrics and LCA aspects.
- Generating results with demonstrated implementation at kg-scale, enabling subsequent piloting and initial market replication.
- Raising awareness about the vast potential of enzymes for the circular bioeconomy and their application to provide greener consumer products.
- Preparing the ground for the exploitation among European citizens of the methods and technologies developed in the project.

In a nutshell, the Plan for Exploitation of results and the Plan for Communication and Dissemination of Results aim to bridge the gap between scientific research and development with the impact on society, environment and the economy.

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